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Study of Stepwise Complexation of Fe(III) with 1-hydroxy phthalaz-4-one in DMF

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SOME phthalazones have attracted much attention in recent years not only on account of their structural ambiguity¹⁻³ and chemiluminescent⁴ properties but also due to their antitubercular activity⁵. Some of the phthalazones were found to be more active than the hydrochlorides of streptomycin and dihydrostreptomycin⁶. Still they have not been placed in medicinal use probably on account of their injurious effect on human tissues. However, one may expect that some non-injurious phthalazone complexes may be of vital importance from medicinal point of view. Practically no attempt has been made with an intention to investigate the possibility of the formation of complexes by phthalazones or substituted phthalazones. The work of Drew and Garwood⁷ to investigate the structure of isomeric N-methylated compounds of 5-nitro-1,4-dihydroxy phthalazine, described as α - and β -series, involves the preparation of Cu(II) complexes of substituted phthalazones, in which both, the phthalazone ring and the substituent occupy the coordination site simultaneously. Therefore, the aim of the present work is to investigate the possibility of formation of complexes by phthalazone with Fe(III), which may be of immense interest to the biochemists and further, to evaluate the thermodynamic properties such as stability constant and the free energy change in the complexation process.

Experimental

Preparation of 1-hydroxy phthalaz-4-one :

The above compound was prepared from phthalic anhydride, hydrazine sulphate and sodium acetate in dilute acetic acid according to the method described by Drew and Hatt⁸. The crude phthalazone recovered as a precipitate by bubbling carbon dioxide in the reaction mixture was crystallised from DMF and was dried in vacuum desiccator. The compound melted at 341-344°.

Preparation of 0.1M Ferric Chloride Solution in DMF :

Ferric chloride (E. Merck quality) was dried in a desiccator containing conc. H₂SO₄ for two weeks and was dissolved in freshly distilled DMF to have a solution of approximately 0.1M. Its strength was accurately determined by volumetric method⁹.

Spectrophotometric Study

Mole Ratio Method¹⁰ :

A series of solutions were prepared by mixing a definite volume of 0.01M ferric chloride solution with varying amounts of 0.01M phthalazone solution in freshly distilled DMF and diluting them with the solvent to a constant volume. The development of colour was studied at 25° by measuring the optical density at regular intervals. The constancy in the absorbance at a particular wave length was observed some time after three days or more. Therefore the absorbance measurements were made well after a week at 530 nm on a Bausch and Lomb spectronic 20 colourimeter using 1 cm effective path. Mean of the absorbances of three specimen of solutions with same metal ligand composition prepared separately was recorded in each case. A graph was obtained by plotting absorbance against the total ligand concentrations (Fig. 1). The absorbances of the

Fig. 1.

ferric chloride solutions of varying concentrations in DMF were also measured and molar absorption coefficient was determined.

The interaction between the solution of Fe(III) ion and phthalazone in DMF was also investigated by Job's method¹¹ of continuous variation.

Results and Discussion

Although a number of methods are available for the calculation of stability constants of complexes with N (total number of complexes) = 2 from spectrophotometric data, the calculation becomes difficult when N is more than 2 and the variation of absorbance as a function of total ligand concentration is monotonic. However extrapolation procedure of Yatsimirskii¹² has been applied in special cases by other workers^{1,3,14}. Newman and Hume¹⁵ have

related molar absorption coefficients with successive stability constants as,

$$\bar{\Delta\epsilon} = \bar{\epsilon} - \epsilon_0 = \frac{\Delta\epsilon_1\beta_1[L] + \Delta\epsilon_2\beta_2[L]^2 + \dots + \Delta\epsilon_N\beta_N[L]^N}{1 + \beta_1[L] + \beta_2[L]^2 + \dots + \beta_N[L]^N}$$

Now applying Yatsimirskii's method^{1a} of extrapolation and assuming only three complexes are being formed, six equations are obtained which on solving yield the expressions for β_1 , β_2 and β_3 in terms of subsidiary functions of g and f . Further, assuming β_1 to be negligible, we get

$$\beta_2 = \frac{f_2g_2 - f_1g_2}{g_2^2 + g_1g_2} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta_3 = -\beta_2 \frac{g_1}{g_2} + \frac{f_2}{g_2}$$

where g_1 , g_2 and f_1 , f_2 have their usual significance.

Our study of the complex equilibria between phthalazone and Fe(III) ion by mole ratio method, shows a change in the slope of absorption curve at two points, one at the metal-ligand ratio of 1 : 2 and another at the metal-ligand ratio of 1 : 3, suggesting the formation of 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes respectively (Fig. 1). Calculation of stabilities on the basis of above procedure also supports the view that two complexes in the ratio 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 are formed. The outline of the calculation of the stability constants adopted here is as follows :

(1) Phthalazone does not absorb in the visible spectral region and therefore molar absorption coefficient, ϵ_x has been taken as zero.

(2) In the extrapolation of f_1 , f_2 , f_3 and g_1 , g_2 , g_3 the total ligand concentration is used in place of free ligand concentration as first approximation.

(3) The values of stability constants calculated from the approximate values of f_1 , f_2 , f_3 and g_1 , g_2 , g_3 are applied to find out free ligand concentration using equation

$$[L] = T_L - T_M \frac{\beta_1[L] + 2\beta_2[L]^2 + 3\beta_3[L]^3}{1 + \beta_1[L] + \beta_2[L]^2 + \beta_3[L]^3}$$

and making successive approximation for the value of $[L]$.

(4) Now these free ligand concentrations corresponding to different total ligand concentrations are used to recalculate the more accurate stability constants by extrapolation method in the way described above.

(5) The procedure for the evaluation of stability constant data is repeated as above in cyclic way till their values are found constant within the limit of precession.

The Table 1 gives only the necessary data required in the calculation of the final values of stability constants.

1-Hydroxy phthalaz-4-one is a monobasic acid even weaker than carbon dioxide and as complexing agent, it appears from its molar structure to be

TABLE 1

Temp. = 25° λ = 530 nm TM = 0.714 × 10 ⁻³ M ε ₀ = 105								
S. No.	T _L × 10 ³	[L] × 10 ³	$\bar{\Delta\epsilon}$	$\Delta\epsilon[L] = f'_1$ × 10 ⁻³	$\frac{f'_1 - f'_2}{[L]} = f'_2$ × 10 ⁶	$(\bar{\Delta\epsilon} - g_1)[L] = g'_1$ × 10 ³	$(g'_2 - g_2)[L] = g'_2$ × 10 ⁶	\bar{n}
1.	0.357	0.351	4.2	11.96	25.52	0.008
2.	0.714	0.686	21.0	30.61	40.24	0.045
3.	1.071	1.000	53.2	53.20	50.20	0.120
4.	1.428	1.288	186.2	144.56	109.90	0.227
5.	1.785	1.570	123.2	0.370
6.	2.142	1.820	100.8	0.521
7.	2.500	2.070	119.0	0.691
8.	2.857	2.318	130.2	0.870
9.	3.571	2.790	140.0	- 142.29	- 0.25	1.212
10.	4.285	3.285	147.0	- 144.54	- 17.98	1.546
11.	5.000	3.792	154.0	- 140.30	7.20	1.830
12.	5.714	4.320	158.2	- 141.69	0.57	2.070

Calculated values of $\beta_2 = (2.1 \pm 0.1) \times 10^4$

and $\beta_3 = (2.8 \pm 0.1) \times 10^7$

$\epsilon_2 = 106.4$

$\epsilon_3 = 296.0$

The molar free energy decrease $-\Delta G = RT \ln K$ were found to be as follows :

$-\Delta G_2 = 5.99$ K cal.

$-\Delta G_3 = 10.15$ K cal.

multidentate ligand having two pairs of chelates in the same ring of the molecule.

The Job's method of continuous variation fails to indicate a definite account of the complexation as the graph shows sufficient rounding at the peak. This seems to support our contention, of course indirectly, that either a weak complex or more than one complexes are being formed. As such the Job's method cannot be employed for any decisive information regarding the metal ligand ratio in the complex.

The spectrophotometric study by mole ratio method and the subsequent calculation of stability constants reveal the following important observations :

(i) The stepwise complexation of the metal and ligand takes place in the ratios 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 which may be represented as ML^{+2} , ML_2^+ and ML_3 respectively.

(ii) The 1 : 1 complex is very much unstable in comparison to the other two complexes formed.

(iii) The stability constant and the corresponding free energy decrease of ML_3 (1 : 3 complex) are much greater than those of ML_2^+ (1 : 2).

On the basis of above conclusions it appears that stability increases with decrease of charge on the metal ion due to chelation and consequent desolvation of the species formed. Thus the stability constant of 1 : 3 complex (ML_3) being maximum appears to be quite reasonable.

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The Kinetics and Mechanism of Alkaline Hydrolysis of *o*-Methoxybenzamide

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THE kinetics of the hydrolysis of *o*-methoxybenzamide was studied under strongly alkaline medium. The observed pseudo first order rate constants were found to follow the empirical relationship

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = B_1 + \frac{B_2}{[\text{OH}^-]}$$

The linear parameters B_1 and B_2 were evaluated using linear least square technique. On the basis of the observed results a plausible mechanism was proposed. The temperature dependence of hydrolysis was also studied and various activation parameters were evaluated.

The kinetics of hydrolysis of *o*-methoxybenzamide was studied by Ried¹ who postulated a second order reaction in dilute acid and base solutions. Bruce and Tanner², while studying the effect of neighbouring hydroxyl groups in amide hydrolysis, gave the pH-rate profile of *o*-methoxybenzamide in very low alkaline range. No work on the hydrolysis of amides in highly alkaline medium has been reported and, therefore, in continuation of our work^{3,4} on this problem under these conditions, it was thought worthwhile to study the hydrolysis of *o*-methoxybenzamide.

Experimental

Materials : *o*-Methoxybenzamide (Aldrich) was used as such without further purification. Its freshly prepared solution in 10% ethanol was used for each set. All the other chemicals were of analytical reagent grade. Nessler's reagent was prepared by the method as described by Vogel⁵.

Kinetic Measurements :

A two-necked flask fitted with a double walled condenser, in order to check any kind of evaporation, was thermostated in an oil bath at the desired temperature. The requisite volumes of all the solutions except sodium hydroxide were taken in the flask. The reaction was started by adding the known volumes of sodium hydroxide solution and zero time was taken when half sodium hydroxide solution was transferred into the flask. As the reaction proceeded, the evolved ammonia was swept out by a continuous current of nitrogen and was absorbed in 0.05 M hydrochloric acid^{6,7} at different time intervals. The absorbed ammonia was then estimated spectrophotometrically by Nesslerization. The spectrophotometric measurements were made on a Bausch and Lomb spectronic-20.